

dsm2cli : A Verifiable and Observable Pipeline for Translating Network Intents into Multivendor CLI

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Abstract. *Network configuration in multivendor environments remains challenging due to semantic inconsistencies and the lack of verifiable intent-to-CLI translation. Existing LLM-based approaches treat generation as a black box, lacking validation, observability, and reproducibility. We present *dsm2cli*, a modular and verifiable pipeline that separates translation and semantic verification, producing traceable artifacts and telemetry under a unified contract. Across six multivendor scenarios, four pipeline configurations, and 72 executions, results show that *dsm2cli* enables controlled comparison, exposes hidden semantic failures, and reveals trade-offs between robustness, cost, and latency.*

1. Introduction

Configuring and operating heterogeneous networks remains challenging, particularly in *multivendor* environments, where syntactic and semantic differences across vendors hinder standardization, portability, and automation [Wallin et al. 2011, Hollósi et al. 2024, Wei et al. 2025]. In practice, network configuration still relies heavily on vendor-specific templates and ad hoc logic, resulting in brittle workflows that are difficult to reuse, validate, and adapt to new scenarios [Leivadeas and Falkner 2023, Ansible Community 2026, Hollósi et al. 2024]. These limitations are exacerbated by subtle semantic divergences across devices, where configurations that are syntactically valid may fail to enforce the intended operational state.

Recent advances have explored the use of large language models (LLMs) to translate high-level intents into device-specific configurations [Long et al. 2025, Hong et al. 2025, Tu et al. 2025, Wei et al. 2025, Lira et al. 2024, Tageldien et al. 2025]. While promising, these approaches largely treat translation as a generation problem, providing limited guarantees about semantic correctness, reproducibility, and observability. In particular, current solutions lack mechanisms to systematically verify whether generated configurations faithfully implement the intended network state, or to compare alternative translation strategies under controlled conditions.

This gap becomes critical in realistic deployment scenarios, where correctness is not solely determined by syntactic validity, but by adherence to high-level intent. As a result, generating CLI commands is insufficient: it is necessary to validate their semantic equivalence to the intended configuration and to capture execution evidence that

supports inspection, debugging, and reproducibility. Moreover, evaluating different translation strategies requires controlled and comparable execution pipelines, where variations in quality, cost, and latency can be systematically analyzed.

Intent-Based Networking (IBN) provides a conceptual foundation for addressing this problem by expressing network behavior through declarative, vendor-independent abstractions, such as *Desired State Models* (DSMs) [Zeydan and Turk 2020, Ansible Community 2026]. However, existing approaches do not provide a unified framework to translate DSMs into CLI configurations while ensuring semantic verification and execution observability.

In this paper, we present *dsm2cli*, a modular and verifiable pipeline for translating structured network intents into multivendor CLI configurations. The proposed approach explicitly separates translation from semantic verification, leveraging independent evaluators to assess adherence between generated configurations and the input intent. All executions follow a unified input–output contract and produce structured artifacts, including traceability data, evaluation votes, aggregated verdicts, and telemetry metrics.

We evaluate *dsm2cli* across six multivendor scenarios, four pipeline configurations, and 72 executions. Our results show that the proposed approach enables controlled comparison of translation strategies, exposes semantic failures that remain undetected in generation-only workflows, and reveals trade-offs between robustness, cost, and latency.

The main contributions of this work are:

- a verifiable and observable pipeline for translating DSMs into multivendor CLI configurations under a unified execution contract;
- a semantic verification mechanism based on independent evaluators and aggregated voting, enabling systematic validation of intent adherence;
- a structured artifact model that provides traceability and telemetry for reproducible and comparable executions;
- an experimental evaluation demonstrating how the approach enables controlled analysis of translation strategies and their trade-offs.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses related work; Section 3 presents the system architecture; Section 4 reports experimental results; and Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Related Work

Table 1 compares prior work across four dimensions: intent abstraction, output artifact, multivendor support, and verification. Next, we highlight key limitations, research, development, and innovation directions, as well as our contribution.

Model-driven approaches. Systems such as NCS [Wallin et al. 2011] and YANG-based pipelines use structured models to reduce vendor dependencies and improve consistency. However, they rely on predefined schemas and tightly coupled workflows, limiting flexibility and preventing observable, reproducible comparison of alternative pipelines.

High-level abstractions. Approaches such as NetBuddy [Wang et al. 2023] raise abstraction through natural language or policy representations. While improving usability,

Table 1. Comparison of related approaches across input abstraction, target artifact, multivendor support, and verification capabilities.

Work	Input	Target	Multivendor	Verification
NCS [Wallin et al. 2011]	NETCONF/YANG	CFG/CLI	✓	✓
INTA [Wei et al. 2025]	CFG/Intent	CFG/CLI	✓	✓
IBN+LLM [Tu et al. 2025]	NL/Intent	CFG	✓	✗
S-Witch [Jeong et al. 2024]	NL	CLI	✗	✓
NetBuddy [Wang et al. 2023]	NL	CFG/API	✗	✓
YANG+LLM [Hollósi et al. 2024]	YANG	NETCONF	✗	✓
dsm2cli (this work)	DSM	CLI	✓	✓

they lack guarantees of semantic equivalence and provide limited support for multivendor evaluation or systematic validation.

LLM-based translation. Recent work leverages LLMs for intent-to-configuration translation (e.g., IBN+LLM [Tu et al. 2025], S-Witch [Jeong et al. 2024], INTA [Wei et al. 2025]). These approaches treat translation as a black-box generation task, with verification either absent or tightly coupled, and without a unified execution model for controlled comparison.

Limitations. Across all categories, two limitations persist: the lack of separation between translation and verification, and the absence of observable, reproducible execution frameworks. These hinder independent validation and systematic comparison of strategies.

Our contribution. We address these gaps with *dsm2cli*, a verifiable and observable pipeline for DSM-to-CLI translation. The system separates translation from semantic verification through independent evaluators and operates under a unified contract, producing structured artifacts such as votes, verdicts, traceability, and telemetry. This enables reproducible experiments and controlled comparison, exposing semantic failures and trade-offs not visible in existing approaches.

3. System Architecture

The *dsm2cli*¹ architecture addresses three limitations identified in existing approaches: the absence of separation between translation and verification, the lack of observable and reproducible execution pipelines, and the inability to systematically compare alternative translation strategies. Figure 1 illustrates the overall architecture, organized into three layers: access, processing core, and artifacts, each with distinct responsibilities for interaction, execution, and observability.

3.1. Access Layer and Unified Contract

The access layer exposes the pipeline through four interfaces: Python module, CLI, Web API, and web UI, all sharing a unified input–output contract. This contract is the foundation of the observable and reproducible execution model: it specifies the target device, the DSM, and the execution components (translator and evaluators), enabling different pipeline configurations to be instantiated declaratively without modifying the external

¹<https://github.com/net2d-community/dsm2cli>

Figure 1. Overview of the *dsm2cli* architecture.

interface. The response assembles the generated CLI, individual votes, an aggregated verdict, and structured artifacts including traceability data, classifications, and telemetry, producing a complete and self-contained execution record. Request and response examples are provided in Appendices B and C.

3.2. Processing Core

Figure 2 details the pipeline execution flow. The processing core coordinates execution from the structured request: the input is validated and the DSM is forwarded to the translator, which produces the CLI configuration for the target device. This enforces a strict separation between translation and verification, a key design decision that prevents the semantic correctness assessment from being conflated with or biased by the generation process itself.

Figure 2. *dsm2cli* processing core (pipeline).

The generated CLI is then submitted to multiple independent evaluators, each analyzing its semantic adherence to the input DSM and producing a vote accompanied by structured evidence and classification. An aggregator consolidates these votes into a final verdict, which is composed into the response alongside all other pipeline artifacts. This chained execution makes it possible to observe not only the translation outcome, but also the internal behavior of each stage, surfacing semantic failures that generation-only workflows leave undetected.

The architecture explicitly does not assume that translation is sufficient to guarantee semantic correctness. By treating verification as a native pipeline stage rather than an external validation step, the design enables independent and unbiased assessment of intent adherence. Pipeline composition is also flexible: translators and evaluators can be

swapped, and associated prompt elements can be versioned, without affecting the external interface or the artifact structure.

3.3. Artifact Layer

The artifact layer aggregates all products generated during execution: generated CLI, votes, verdict, traceability evidence, and telemetry. Structured evidence links DSM elements to specific CLI segments, enabling precise localization of semantic deviations, such as the missing `enabled` state observed in Huawei scenarios. Metrics including latency and token consumption support the analysis of trade-offs across translation strategies and underpin the reproducibility of experiments.

Together, these three layers realize the unified execution contract described in the introduction: a verifiable and observable pipeline in which translation, semantic verification, and telemetry are first-class concerns rather than external additions. This positions *dsm2cli* not only as a translation tool, but as a controlled experimentation environment for analyzing and comparing intent-to-CLI strategies in multivendor settings.

4. Experimental Evaluation

This section presents the experimental evaluation of *dsm2cli* across a controlled multivendor matrix. The evaluation is designed to demonstrate three capabilities introduced by the proposed approach: (i) the ability to execute and compare different translation pipelines under a unified input–output contract; (ii) the ability to detect semantic failures through independent verification, which would remain undetected in generation-only workflows; and (iii) the ability to expose trade-offs between robustness, cost, and latency across pipeline configurations.

4.1. Experimental Setup

The evaluation was conducted over six reproducible multivendor scenarios, obtained by combining three use cases with two target vendors: **UC1** (L2 port in access mode), **UC2** (L2 port in tagged mode with an untagged VLAN), and **UC3** (IPv4 addressing on an L3 interface), each instantiated for both **Cisco** and **Huawei** devices.

Four pipeline profiles were defined by varying only the primary translator while keeping three independent evaluators distinct from the translator to prevent self-assessment: **P1** (OpenAI), **P2** (DeepSeek), **P3** (Gemini), and **P4** (XAI/Grok). Each profile was executed three times per scenario, yielding $4 \times 6 \times 3 = 72$ total executions.

For each execution, *dsm2cli* produced: (i) the generated CLI; (ii) individual votes from three independent evaluators; (iii) an aggregated verdict; and (iv) telemetry comprising per-stage latency and token consumption. A verdict is considered *correct* when the aggregated vote reaches majority approval across the three independent evaluators. The version used in this experiment incorporates prompt refinements emphasizing semantic equivalence, explicit creation of normative objects, and suppression of speculative structural inferences about device inventory.

4.2. Functional Results

Table 2 summarizes the functional behavior of the four pipeline profiles across the six scenarios. Each cell reports the number of correct executions out of three repetitions and the mean number of favorable votes (μ) across the three evaluators (max. $\mu = 3.0$).

Profiles P1 and P3 achieved full correctness across all 18 executions. P3 (Gemini) reached perfect evaluator consensus ($\mu=3.00$) in five of six scenarios, with a minor deviation only in UC3–Cisco ($\mu=2.67$). P1 (OpenAI) exhibited equally robust correctness, with deviations in evaluator consensus restricted to UC3–Cisco ($\mu=2.67$), indicating that the generated CLI was accepted but not unanimously considered optimal. Both profiles demonstrated stable behavior across all three repetitions per scenario, with no variance in the correctness outcome.

Table 2. Functional results per scenario and pipeline profile across three repetitions. Each cell reports correct executions out of three and mean favorable votes μ (max. 3.0).

Scenario	P1 (OpenAI)	P2 (DeepSeek)	P3 (Gemini)	P4 (XAI)
UC1 – Cisco	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	3/3; $\mu=2.33$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$
UC2 – Cisco	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	3/3; $\mu=2.67$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	3/3; $\mu=2.67$
UC3 – Cisco	3/3; $\mu=2.67$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$
UC1 – Huawei	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	0/3; $\mu=1.00$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	0/3; $\mu=1.00$
UC2 – Huawei	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	3/3; $\mu=2.67$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	3/3; $\mu=2.00$
UC3 – Huawei	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	0/3; $\mu=0.00$	3/3; $\mu=3.00$	0/3; $\mu=1.00$
Total	18/18	12/18	18/18	12/18

All profiles succeeded on Cisco scenarios. UC1, UC2, and UC3 on Cisco were correctly solved by all four profiles across all three repetitions, suggesting that Cisco CLI conventions for the evaluated use cases are sufficiently well-represented in the translators’ training data to produce semantically correct outputs regardless of the specific model used.

Huawei scenarios exposed discriminating failures in P2 and P4. Profiles P2 (DeepSeek) and P4 (XAI) failed consistently in UC1–Huawei and UC3–Huawei: all three repetitions were rejected in both cases, yielding 0/3 correct executions with zero variance in outcome. This consistency rules out random generation noise and indicates systematic semantic deficiencies in the translated CLI for those scenarios. The most critical case is P2–UC3–Huawei, which obtained $\mu=0.00$ — the only instance in the experiment where all three independent evaluators unanimously rejected every repetition. This represents a complete and reproducible semantic failure: the generated CLI was not merely imprecise, but structurally inconsistent with the intended network state as expressed in the DSM.

The verification mechanism reveals failures that syntactic inspection would not detect. In all failing cases, the generated CLI was syntactically plausible and would not be flagged by a parser or a generation-only pipeline. The independent evaluators identified semantic omissions, most notably the absence of an explicit `enabled` state on Huawei interfaces, where the CLI did not guarantee that the interface would be operationally active after configuration. This class of failure is invisible without semantic verification tied to the input intent, which directly addresses the limitation identified in generation-only approaches such as IBN+LLM [Tu et al. 2025]. UC2–Huawei exhibited partial robustness in P4 ($\mu=2.00$), suggesting that the same deficiency manifests with varying severity depending on the structural complexity of the use case.

4.3. Telemetry and Cost Analysis

Beyond functional correctness, *dsm2cli* produced structured telemetry enabling systematic analysis of execution cost and latency across profiles. Tables 3 and 4 report per-profile

performance metrics averaged across all 18 executions (six scenarios, three repetitions).

Table 3. Telemetry summary per pipeline profile: correctness, mean evaluator votes, and mean execution latency across three repetitions.

Profile	Correct executions	Mean votes ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Mean latency (s)
P1 (OpenAI)	18/18	2.944 ± 0.236	68.770 ± 42.699
P2 (DeepSeek)	12/18	1.944 ± 1.056	55.740 ± 34.094
P3 (Gemini)	18/18	3.000 ± 0.000	51.957 ± 27.763
P4 (XAI)	12/18	2.111 ± 0.832	53.218 ± 23.830

P3 dominates on both correctness and efficiency. Gemini achieved full correctness (18/18), perfect evaluator consensus ($\sigma=0.000$), the lowest mean latency (51.957 s), and the second-lowest total token consumption (8124.9 tokens). This combination makes P3 the Pareto-optimal profile in the evaluated matrix: no other profile achieves the same correctness at lower cost or lower latency.

P1 incurs the highest cost for equivalent correctness. OpenAI achieved the same 18/18 correctness as Gemini but at substantially higher resource expenditure: mean latency 32% higher (68.770 vs. 51.957 s) and translator token consumption 147% higher (3628.1 vs. 1467.4 tokens). The high variance in both latency (± 42.699 s, coefficient of variation 62%) and translator token count (± 1092.3) suggests that the OpenAI model produces outputs of highly variable verbosity depending on the scenario, which propagates cost to the evaluator stage: a more verbose CLI requires more tokens to analyze, explaining why total token consumption also remains elevated even though evaluator prompts are shared across profiles.

Latency variance is high across all profiles and must be interpreted cautiously. Coefficients of variation range from 52% (P4) to 62% (P1 and P2). This level of variance is consistent with provider-side factors including request queuing, model cold starts, and network conditions, which are external to the pipeline and not controlled in this experiment. Latency comparisons should therefore be treated as indicative rather than definitive. Controlled benchmarking under fixed infrastructure conditions is left as future work.

Table 4. Resource consumption per pipeline profile: mean translator token usage, mean total token usage, and mean processing throughput across three repetitions.

Profile	Translator tokens (mean)	Total tokens (mean)	Throughput (tokens/s)
P1 (OpenAI)	3628.1 ± 1092.3	8675.2 ± 1081.2	145.407 ± 41.070
P2 (DeepSeek)	1395.9 ± 34.0	8249.1 ± 1549.8	178.746 ± 57.828
P3 (Gemini)	1467.4 ± 40.8	8124.9 ± 1325.1	170.075 ± 42.022
P4 (XAI)	1298.5 ± 47.7	8068.1 ± 1769.4	172.513 ± 54.232

Total token consumption is structurally dominated by evaluators, not the translator. For P2, P3, and P4, translator tokens represent 17–20% of total token consumption (e.g., P4: 1298.5 of 8068.1). For P1, the translator accounts for 42% (3628.1 of 8675.2). This indicates that in efficient profiles, the verification stage (three independent evaluators) is responsible for approximately 80% of total token cost, a consequence of the independent evaluation design. This ratio is an inherent characteristic of the architecture and a deliberate trade-off: the cost of verification is the cost of semantic correctness guarantees.

4.4. Discussion

The results demonstrate that *dsm2cli* fulfills its role as a controlled experimentation platform.

Controlled comparison under a unified contract. All profiles were executed under identical inputs, evaluation policies, and output schemas. The observed differences, namely full correctness for P1 and P3 and systematic failures for P2 and P4 in Huawei scenarios, are attributable solely to the translator, with all other components held constant. This level of isolation is not achievable in generation-only workflows.

Semantic failure detection beyond syntactic validity. Failures in P2 and P4 were not syntactic but semantic: the generated CLIs were well-formed yet incomplete. Independent evaluators detected omissions such as the missing explicit `enabled` state on Huawei interfaces by reasoning against the DSM. This validates the separation between translation and verification. The case P2–UC3–Huawei (=0.00) shows that failures are systematic and reproducible, and would have been silently accepted in the absence of independent verification, underscoring its necessity.

Trade-off visibility across robustness, cost, and latency. Telemetry shows that correctness and efficiency are not correlated. P3 achieves the best overall balance, while P1 matches correctness at higher cost, and P2 and P4 reduce cost at the expense of robustness. These trade-offs are observable only because *dsm2cli* enforces a unified contract and produces structured telemetry, a capability absent in systems such as INTA [Wei et al. 2025] and NetBuddy [Wang et al. 2023].

5. Conclusions and Future Work

This paper presented *dsm2cli*, a verifiable and observable pipeline for translating structured network intents (DSMs) into multivendor CLI configurations, addressing two key limitations of prior work: the lack of separation between translation and verification, and the absence of controlled, reproducible execution for comparing strategies. The architecture decouples translation from semantic verification through independent evaluators under a unified input–output contract, producing structured artifacts such as votes, verdicts, traceability, and telemetry.

Evaluation across six scenarios, four pipeline profiles, and 72 executions shows that the unified contract enables controlled comparison, independent verification exposes semantic failures missed by generation-only approaches, and telemetry reveals trade-offs between robustness, cost, and latency. P3 achieves the best balance, while P1 incurs higher cost for equivalent correctness.

Availability and demonstration details are provided in Appendix A. Future work will expand scenario coverage, enhance verification strategies, and integrate execution with real or emulated environments, positioning *dsm2cli* as a foundation for reproducible evaluation of intent-to-CLI pipelines.

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Apêndices

A. Availability, Demonstration, and Reproducibility

The *dsm2cli* artifact associated with this work is publicly available at <https://github.com/net2d-community/dsm2cli>, including source code, documentation, usage examples, and scripts required for execution and evaluation. The environment can be instantiated in a standardized manner using Docker Compose, enabling rapid deployment of both the Web API and the Web interface with minimal configuration effort. Alternatively, local execution via Python is also supported.

The repository provides example requests, automated tests, and a dedicated directory for reproducing the experiments reported in this paper, allowing independent verification of the presented results. All components operate under a unified input–output contract, ensuring consistency across executions.

The demonstration can be performed on modest hardware (e.g., a standard laptop running an Ubuntu 20.04 virtual machine with 4 vCPUs and 8 GB RAM), without requiring specialized infrastructure or dedicated network environments, as models are accessed remotely. In addition, an offline (stub) mode is available for inspecting the execution contract and generated artifacts without relying on external providers, further enhancing accessibility, auditability, and reproducibility.

B. Example of a *dsm2cli* request structure

Lista 1. Example of a *dsm2cli* request structure

```
{
  "device": {
    "manufacturer": "cisco",
    "platform": "nxos"
  },
  "dsm": {
    "interface": {
      "name": "Ethernet1/1",
      "mode": "access",
      "enabled": true,
      "untagged_vlan": { "vid": 20, "name": "usuarios" }
    }
  },
  "translator": {
    "provider": "openai",
    "model": "gpt-4o"
  },
  "judges": [
    { "provider": "openai", "model": "gpt-4o-mini" },
    { "provider": "deepseek", "model": "deepseek-chat" }
  ]
}
```

C. Example of a structured output generated by the *dsm2cli* pipeline

Lista 2. Example of a structured output generated by the *dsm2cli* pipeline

```
{
  "translation": {
    "status": "success",
    "cli_lines": [
      "interface Ethernet1/1",
      "switchport",
      "switchport mode access",
      "switchport access vlan 20",
      "no shutdown"
    ]
  },
  "votes": [
    { "judge": "gpt-4o-mini", "verdict": "correct" },
    { "judge": "deepseek-chat", "verdict": "correct" }
  ],
  "summary": {
    "final_verdict": "correct"
  },
  "telemetry": {
    "translator_latency_ms": 1820
  }
}
```